

The Impact of Web Based Education on Cancer Patients' Clinical Outcomes

Authors : F. Arıkan, Z. Karakus

Abstract : Cancer is a widespread disease in the world and is the third reason of deaths among the chronic diseases. Educating patients and caregivers has a vital role for empowering them in managing disease and treatment's symptoms. Informing of the patients about their disease and treatment process decreases patient's distress and decisional conflicts, improves wellbeing of them, increase success of the treatment and survival. In this era, technological education methods are used for patients that have different chronic disease. Many studies indicated that especially web based patient education such as chronic obstructive lung disease; heart failure is more effective than printed materials. Web based education provide easiness to patients while they are reaching health services. It also has more advantages because of it decreases health cost and requirement of staff. It is thought that web based education may be beneficial method for cancer patient's empowerment in coping with the disease's symptoms. The aim of the study is evaluate the effectiveness of web based education for cancer patients' clinical outcomes.

Keywords : cancer patients, e-learning, nursing, web based education

Conference Title : ICEEEL 2014 : International Conference on e-Education and e-Learning

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : May 19-20, 2014